

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP8: Scientific coordination, project management & sustainability

D8.2 Collaborative Website (intranet)

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	V1.0	1 April 2019

Document History

Version	Date	Description	Non-contributor reviewers (if applicable)
V1.0	21 June 2019	First Draft	Not applicable
V1.1	05 July 2019	Final Version	Not applicable

Publishable Summary

The main objective of WP8 is to run an effective project management for the ConcePTION consortium and to guarantee the project's long-lasting effect on rapid and adequate information on the effects of drugs during pregnancy and lactation for women, society and pharmacovigilance.

A collaborative website contributes to running an effective project management as it makes sure the consortium members have access to and can share important project- and work package documents in a secured area.

Methods

A collaborative website (<https://www.imi-conception.eu/memberarea>) has been developed as the initial collaborative website and launched at the ConcePTION kick-off meeting in April 2019. In the near future, a public project website will be developed and launched (D8.6 Public website and social media plan). The existing member area will be transferred to the new public website.

The goal of the collaborative website is to share relevant consortium and work package documents and archive important project material in a secured area. These documents are only accessible and available for consortium members, as the 'member area' is secured with a personal user account (figure 1). When the member area is transferred to the new public website, the member area will stay secured with a personal user account. Florian van der Nolle (UMCU) from the PMO team is responsible for the creating, managing and, if needed, deleting of the personal user accounts. The user accounts contain an email address, username (same as email address), display name (first and last name) and password. The account details are safely stored on the secured hard drive at the UMCU.

Results

The collaborative website consists of a general, management team, management board and work package area (figure 2). The general section houses important project documents, for example, contract, contact lists, project reports and templates (figure 3). On the management board section, the minutes from the previous management board meetings can be accessed by the whole all consortium members (figure 4). Both the general area and the management board area are accessible for all members, however, the PMO is responsible for uploading the documents and keeping these sections up to date.

Each work package has its own assigned page, within the work package area, where consortium members can edit, add and delete content themselves (figure 5). It is up to every work package on how to structure and use their work package page.

Discussion

No deviations from the description of work for this deliverable.

Annex

Figure 1: Login page ConcePTION member area

Figure 2: Homepage ConcePTION member area

Figure 3: General section on ConcePTION member area

General Information

Figure 4: Management board section on ConcePTION member area

Documents

Figure 5: Work package 1 section on ConcePTION member area

The screenshot shows a web interface for the 'Member Area'. On the left is a navigation menu with items: Consortium Information, Management Team, Management Board, Work Package 1 (highlighted), Work Package 2, Work Package 3, Work Package 4, Work Package 5, Work Package 6, Work Package 7, and Work Package 8. The main content area features a large image of a woman breastfeeding a baby under a tree, with a 'Welcome to Conception' text box overlaid. Below the image, the 'Work Package 1' section is titled 'Moving beyond pregnancy registries to enhance our understanding of disease-related pregnancy outcomes, medication use and safety of use during pregnancy'. Underneath, the 'Objectives' section states: 'The overall objective of WP1 is to generate timely evidence about pregnancy outcomes, including perinatal and long-term effects following medication use during pregnancy, to benefit women, their babies and their families. The aim is to move beyond medication exposure pregnancy registries by continuously identifying secondary data sources*, optimising analytic methods and tools, and identifying the strengths and limitations of different approaches to generate actionable evidence on medication use and safety in pregnancy including maternal (pregnancy), perinatal and childhood outcomes'. To the right, the 'WP Leads' section contains two redacted names, each preceded by a small icon.